

Synthesis and characterization of Ba²⁺ doped NdCoO₃ as potential cathode materials for SOFCs application

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Abstract: Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) have attracted great attention in electrochemical devices because of their high energy conversion efficiency, pollution free and widely flexible fuel choices [1, 2]. However, the high operating temperature of about 800 °C - 1000°C leads to technological hurdles in SOFCs technology due to thermal expansion mismatch, chemical reactivity among the components and long term durability [3-5]. These difficulties could be minimized by lowering the operating temperature; nevertheless it reduces the electrode kinetics. Hence, there is a need for the development of alternate cathode materials. The present work aims to develop nanocrystalline Ba²⁺ doped NdCoO₃ perovskite oxides materials for ITSOFC applications. Nanocrystalline Ba²⁺ doped NdCoO₃ samples were prepared by using combustion process and characterized by XRD, FTIR and SEM-EDX techniques. Further the thermal expansion, chemical compatibility, and electrochemical performance of the prepared Ba²⁺ doped NdCoO₃ materials were investigated. Detailed results will be presented and discussed.

Key words: Combustion Process, Perovskite oxides, XRD, SEM-EDX and Electrical conductivity.

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